

Part 2 Archiving Wizard - Active Projects VIHDAS DIGITALES

This form will collect the documentary products created in Part 1 for submission to the digital repository (open-access or institutional).

You should use this form only if you have completed the [PART 1 of the Digital Documentation Process \(DDP\) Archiving Wizard for Active Projects](#) (the LIGHT GREEN form), and you have received the responses from that process or from your project cataloguer. PART 2 of the Archiving Wizard will help you complete the archiving of your digital work.

It will collect four different products which were created in cooperation with the cataloguer. These are:

1. The project catalogue record (URL) and persistent identifier (DOI);
2. A web recording of the project in its active phase;
3. A site map;
4. The final version of your Archiving Dossier Narrative.

If you have already uploaded the webrecording and/or a sitemap, please skip sections 3 and 4.

Email
prdivo@gmail.com

Are you working with a cataloguer at your institution to archive your digital project?
Yes

Please provide the email of the cataloguer at your institution.
A00194036@tec.mx

II.1. Creating Citable Project Documentation

Please paste the URL link to the project's Catalogue Record.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6383696>

Please add to DOI of the project's persistent identifier here. This information should be generated by the open-access repository or provided to you by your institution's cataloguer.
10.5281/zenodo.6383696

VERY IMPORTANT: You should now manually insert the DOI and Catalogue Record URL to the top of your Archiving Dossier Narrative.

II. 4. Cataloguing/Archiving Site Content: The Archiving Dossier Narrative

You should have received a rough draft of the Archiving Dossier Narrative from the responses you entered in PART 1 of the Archiving Wizard. **Make sure to manually insert the newly-created DOI and Catalogue Record at the top of the document, created in PART 1 of the DDP.** Remember that your final draft should be of publishable quality, ideally for inclusion in a field-specific journal of your choosing. The goal of the narrative is to communicate the value of the project to all users and audiences.

Complete Cataloguing

All components of the DDP will be assembled upon completion of this form, and archivers will be sent

notification of its completion. Archivers should enter the collected digital objects (WARC file, PDFs of site map and Archiving Dossier Narrative) into the digital repository, whether open access or institution-based.

Thank you for using the Digital Documentation Process to catalogue your digital work. You should now be able to cite your work confidently, as all materials are stored in their most durable file formats.